

**Developing Gender-Awareness and Inclusivity in Teaching in
Business and Management Schools**

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Abstract

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Gender inequality patterns in Business and Management (B&M) Schools show little signs of diminishing and, in some cases, have been increasing (Fotaki, 2013; Śliwa et al., 2022). Academics in B&M Schools from a wide range of disciplines with different epistemological and ontological perspectives and research approaches in knowledge production have also increased the complexity of advancing gender equality in B&M Schools. B&M Schools are responsible for shaping equal and inclusive cultures in organisations to meet contemporary requirements, as they are at the forefront of fostering prospective business and organisational managers, leaders, and entrepreneurs to address management and business challenges. Given the impact of gender-aware and inclusive teaching in shaping students' experience and their future employability, the presentation will share the bespoke guide developed by the Lancaster University Management School's (LUMS) TARGETED-MPI Project team: *The Guide to Developing a Gender-Aware and Inclusive Curriculum (GIC)* and introduce how to use this Guide. With a focus on the importance of practising gender awareness and inclusivity in pedagogical development, GIC has been created for Module Convenors to reflect on as they develop, update and deliver their modules. It is also useful for Programme and Teaching Directors to consider when reviewing their undergraduate and postgraduate programmes. As important building blocks in gender equality planning, integrating the gender dimension in teaching is crucial to advancing gender equality in Higher Education Institutions (European Commission, 2021). Therefore, the presentation will also reflect the team's experiences, as a case study, of moving forward with the agenda to integrate the gender dimension in teaching and how these actions impact colleagues and the School. Discussions and knowledge exchange at the 'marketplace' table will provide an opportunity to explore developing a sustainable action plan to integrate a gender-aware and inclusive lens in everyday teaching and learning practices, as well as the challenges and significance of implementation. Through this community of practice, participants can reflect and discuss their potential bespoke content and strategies to be applied in their faculty, schools, programmes, or pedagogic development. Participants who undertake, manage, and supervise substantial teaching and learning activities and senior management members who develop educational strategies will benefit from this session by exploring action planning for more inclusive management education, hearing about others' experiences and including the opportunity to engage with and discuss a guide developed specifically for the B&M school context.